

Quinazolines. Part IV.

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Recently a number of alkaloids containing a quinazoline ring have been found in nature, *e.g.* vasicine, evodiamine, rutaecarpine, etc. In this paper some quinazolines are described prepared by the method indicated by Beri, Narang and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 395). 6-Nitropiperonylamide has been reduced to 6-aminopiperonylamide (I). Condensation with suitable acid furnish the acyl derivatives (II) which easily cyclise to the quinazoline (III.)

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Nitropiperonal was prepared by the method of Singh and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 640).^{*}

6-Nitropiperonal (5 g.) was oxidised in alkaline suspension with potassium permanganate solution (5%, 54 c.c.) during $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with shaking at 40–60°. Finally the reaction was completed on the boiling water-bath for $\frac{1}{4}$ hour. The acid isolated in the usual way had m.p. 175° after crystallisation, yield 3.5 g.

6-Nitropiperonyl Amide.—6-Nitro-3:4-methylenedioxybenzoic acid (8 g.) suspended in thionyl chloride (20 c. c., freshly distilled) was refluxed on the steam-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then the excess of thionyl chloride removed in *vacuo*. The brownish yellow acid chloride was poured over ammonium carbonate (finely powdered, 25 g.) and the mixture heated on the steam-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After extraction with water, the nitroamide was obtained from the residue in brownish plates after crystallisation from hot water, m.p. 191–93°. [Found (after drying at 110°): N, 13.29. $C_8H_6O_5N_2$ requires N, 13.3 per cent].

6-Aminopiperonyl Amide.—The foregoing nitroamide (1 g.) was added in well powdered form to a solution of stannous chloride (3 g.) in hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.16, 3 c.c.) kept at 50–60°. The mixture was finally warmed to 70° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then cooled in ice. The separated tin double compound was dissolved in the smallest amount of water and basified in the ice cold and extracted with ethyl

The nitration of veratric aldehyde described in this paper is incorrectly described to proceed at 5–10°. It should be at 30–35°. The yield is quantitative.

acetate. The residue after removal of the solvent crystallised from hot water, m. p. $172-74^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 15.43. $C_8H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 15.5 per cent).

6-Acetylamino-3:4-methylenedioxybenzamide.—The foregoing amide (0.9 g.) and pyridine (0.4 g.) dissolved in benzene (5 c.c.) were treated with acetyl chloride (0.4 g.) and the mixture warmed for 10 minutes. After addition of water and removal of solvent, the product was crystallised from hot water, m. p. 212° . (Found: N, 12.5. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 12.6 per cent).

The quinazoline (III, R = Me) was prepared by dissolving the acetylamino compound (0.5 g.) in alcohol (25 c.c.) and treating the solution with sodium hydroxide solution (7.2 c.c., 1%). The mixture after warming to $40-50^{\circ}$ for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour was acidified with acetic acid and the product crystallised from water, m. p. 346° . (Found: N, 13.67. $C_{10}H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.7 per cent).

The substance (II, R = $CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot COOH$) was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 6-amino-3:4-methylenedioxybenzamide (0.9 g.), benzene (20 c.c.), and succinic anhydride (0.5 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After cooling the aminic acid was filtered and then crystallised from water, m. p. 219° , yield 1 g. (Found: N, 10.16. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6N_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent).

The substance (III, R = $CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot COOH$) was prepared by dissolving the substance described above (0.8 g.) in sodium hydroxide (22 c.c., 1%) and warming the solution at 100° for $\frac{1}{4}$ hour. After acidification with acetic acid, the product was crystallised from hot water in silky needles, m. p. 271° , yield 0.65 g. (Found: N, 10.56. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires N, 10.68 per cent).

Similarly, the butyryl derivatives (II, R = $CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH_3$) was prepared from butyryl chloride and the product crystallised in delicate needles from water, m. p. 184° . (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4N_2$ requires N, 11.6 per cent). It (0.7 g) was cyclised to III (R = *n*-propyl) in alcoholic solution (20 c.c.) with 1% sodium hydroxide solution (1 mol.) on steam-bath by heating for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The product, isolated as described before, crystallised from hot water in needles, m. p. 280° , yield 0.6 g. (Found: N, 12.1. Calc for $C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_2$: N, 12.06 per cent).

Most of the analyses recorded above were done by the micro-method.

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